

Elemental & Cyrene Reefs

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The *Revo:oveR* installation is a collection of six co-located installations exploring multimodal interaction, self-evolving aural and visual fabric, integration of architectural space, and the notion of communal art. The interactive aural communal soundscape *Elemental* and one of the two physical sculptures titled *Cyrene Reefs* exhibited at NIME 2009 can be seen as the core aural components of the overall exhibit, latter also exploring the notions of a musical instrument, traditional performance practice, and its ties to the tactile and visual domains.

Using motion tracking in conjunction with a ceiling-mounted 12-speaker array "Elemental" harvests physical motion of visitors populating the exhibit space and augments their location and trajectory with water ripples that refract from the walls and collide with each other, thus generating a surreal sensation of traversing waist-deep water. As an acknowledgment of visitors' communal presence, the collisions among individual ripples are accompanied by aural fireworks, a collection of algorithmically synthesized aural pebbles, ultimately resulting in an ever-changing soundscape that transforms the architectural space into a musical box of infinite possibilities.

Cyrene Reefs complements *Elemental* as an intricate mythical instrument. Populated with holes and fissures resembling stops of a woodwind instrument, the Reef begs to be explored by hands. Its output consists of a cross-pollination of aural and visual, observation, and self-reflection. Akin to the notion of virtuosity, the Reef reveals little of its true potential to the impatient, rewarding only those who choose to persist.